

Appendix 1. PICOC Terms

The PICOC terms considered for this research are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Table captions should be placed above the tables.

PICOC Element	Definition	Applied in This Study
Population	Refers to the group of people or entities being studied. It is the population on which the research is conducted.	Agile software development teams
Intervention	This is what is being tested, applied, or evaluated to see its effect on the population. It can be a treatment, program, technology, technique, or action that is implemented.	Use of gamification in productivity factors of the Meaning category
Comparison	This is the condition against which the intervention is compared. It is not always required, but it is used when you want to evaluate if the intervention produces better results compared to something else.	Not applicable
Outcome	These are the effects or results measured in the research.	Team productivity factors of the Meaning category
Context	Describes the environment or conditions in which the research is conducted. It may include the location, type of population, or specific circumstances affecting the study.	Software industry, Academia